

Challenges Faced by Tribal Women in India

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Abstract

This study examines the multidimensional challenges faced by tribal women in India, particularly in Maharashtra, focusing on their educational deprivation, health inequalities, economic marginalisation, and socio-cultural vulnerabilities. Despite national efforts such as the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan and rising literacy rates among Scheduled Tribes, tribal girls continue to encounter barriers like poverty, language gaps, inadequate schooling facilities, early marriage, and gender discrimination. Health indicators further highlight severe disparities, with high levels of malnutrition, anaemia, maternal and child mortality, and poor access to essential healthcare in remote tribal regions. Recent research also reveals alarmingly high underweight and malnutrition rates among tribal women due to socio-economic constraints, cultural practices, and lack of basic amenities. These intersecting forms of deprivation impact their social status, economic participation, and political representation. The study underscores the urgent need for inclusive development policies, culturally sensitive education models, improved healthcare delivery, and empowerment-oriented interventions to enhance the overall well-being and dignity of tribal women.

Tribal women face numerous challenges related to education, health, economic equality, and social justice. These challenges include poverty, child marriage, domestic violence, workplace discrimination, and lack of access to healthcare facilities. Additionally, cultural and environmental changes also affect their traditional way of life. Girls in rural areas encounter major problems such as gender discrimination, household responsibilities, unsafe surroundings, poverty, early marriage, and lack of toilet facilities. Such issues negatively impact the education of Scheduled Tribe girls and make their lives increasingly difficult.

Introduction

Malnutrition is a serious concern in tribal regions. Therefore, it is essential to give priority to pregnant women in these areas in order to reduce maternal and child mortality rates in tribal communities. If women receive timely and free services such as blood tests, sonography, consultation with gynaecologists, and proper medical treatment from institutions like Bethany Hospital, it helps create health awareness among them. When prenatal, perinatal, and postnatal care is provided effectively, tribal parents become aware of the importance of essential

medicines for pregnant mothers and newborns. This also helps eliminate superstitions and misleading beliefs prevalent in the villages.

The Literacy Rate (LR) for Scheduled Tribes (STs) has increased from 8.53 percent in 1961 to 58.96 percent in 2011, whereas the LR of the total population has increased from 28.30 percent from 1961 to 72.99 percent in 2011. From 2001 to 2011, the LR increased by 11.86 percentage points for STs and 8.15 percentage points for the entire population. The Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) is currently implemented as India's most important program for universalizing elementary education. In the post-Independence period, sincere efforts were made for the economic and educational development of tribes but still, the performance of the tribes in education is much lower than the Scheduled Castes and non-scheduled tribal population. They had been subjected to various forms of deprivation such as alienation from land and other resources. Tribal women, in particular, had also been facing deprivation of various basic amenities like- health issues, water availability, primary education, etc.

To understand the exact prevalence of malnutrition among tribal women in Maharashtra, the daily newspaper *Pudhari* contacted the Tata Institute of Social Sciences. Researchers Sapna Rokade, Mithun Mog, and Nasim Ahmed Mondal have conducted a study on this subject. Their research revealed that 37.4 percent of tribal women in the state are underweight. These findings are based on the study of 3,923 tribal women between the ages of 15 and 49. This research paper has been published in the journal *Clinical Epidemiology and Global Health*.

According to Sapna Rokade, a BMI below 18.5 is classified as malnutrition. She stated that the prevalence of malnutrition among tribal women in Maharashtra is extremely high, and the reasons behind this are economic, social, and cultural. Many tribal mothers themselves are underweight, resulting in low birth weight of their babies. Early marriage, inadequate nutrition, poor economic conditions, and health-related superstitions are some of the major contributing factors, she added. Women from Pokalevadi further mentioned that basic facilities such as clean water and healthcare are lacking in tribal areas, which adversely affects women's health.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To assess the social status of tribal women
2. To examine the educational condition of tribal women
3. To study the health status of tribal women
4. To analyze the economic condition of tribal women
5. To understand the political participation and status of tribal women

Research Methodology:

The present study is based on secondary data sources, including various reports, newspapers, and published research studies.

Problems Faced by Tribal Women

1. Lack of Education:

The Right to Education has been an important step towards educational development for marginalized communities. However, such schemes and laws are not implemented with the required sensitivity and commitment, largely due to deep-rooted social inequalities. Because literacy rates are low in tribal societies, women remain deprived of educational and employment opportunities. As a result, education is severely lacking in the remote areas where tribal communities live. Moreover, non-tribal teachers are often unwilling to work in tribal regions far away from cities, which further affects the educational future of tribal children. Despite compulsory and free education, children are dropping out of school as rapidly as leaves fall from trees. This situation demands comprehensive and collective efforts for improvement.

2. Language Barriers:

Many tribal women face difficulties communicating in languages other than their native tribal dialects. Language barriers are evident at multiple levels, especially in education and administration, where the gap between local dialects and standard languages creates challenges. This makes learning difficult for students, increases their sense of isolation, and often leads to school dropout. To address this, primary education should be provided in the mother tongue, educational materials should be made available in local dialects, and teachers should be trained in local languages.

3. Lack of Skill Development:

Due to inadequate education and limited opportunities for skill development, women remain economically weak. Skill development is insufficient in tribal communities for several reasons, such as language barriers, lack of education, shortage of resources, and socio-cultural constraints. These issues make it difficult for women to access employment opportunities and keep them away from the mainstream. Leaders who truly understand tribal issues are rarely seen in politics; those who are present lack genuine commitment to tribal welfare. Many take advantage of tribal ignorance and simplicity for religious conversion or personal financial gain.

4. Health and Nutrition:

Tribal communities face severe shortages in health facilities. Remote areas lack proper healthcare infrastructure, negatively impacting the health of women and children. Due to poverty and lack of awareness about nutritious food, women suffer from malnutrition and anemia.

According to the National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), 2019–21, the Infant Mortality Rate (IMR) and Under-5 Mortality Rate (U5MR) among Scheduled Tribe children are 42 and 50 per 1,000 live births, respectively, compared to 28 and 33 among more privileged groups. Between 2005–06 and 2019–21, improvements in Neonatal Mortality Rate (NMR) and

IMR were the lowest among Scheduled Tribe children. In terms of nutrition, 41% of tribal children are stunted, 40% are underweight, and 72% suffer from anemia—higher than any other group in the country.

Though Maharashtra is one of India's most industrially and economically advanced states, its tribal regions show some of the deepest inequalities in health and nutrition. Maharashtra has nearly 10.5 million tribal people, accounting for about 9.4% of the state's population, making it the second-highest after Madhya Pradesh. Districts like Gadchiroli, Nandurbar, Palghar, Nashik, Thane, Amravati, and Chandrapur have large tribal populations and face challenges such as hilly terrain, remoteness, poor infrastructure, and high poverty levels. These areas consistently suffer from malnutrition, high maternal and child mortality rates, and lack of quality healthcare. Despite decades of policies, basic health and nutrition rights remain out of reach for many tribal families.

4. Child Marriage and Gender Discrimination:

Problems such as child marriage and gender discrimination make women's lives extremely difficult. Social practices like child marriage and female foeticide reflect deep-rooted gender biases and have severe impacts on women's health, rights, and social status. Malnutrition among tribal children and women in Maharashtra is a silent yet persistent emergency. According to NFHS-5, 41% of tribal children under the age of five are stunted, around 32% are severely malnourished, and more than 46% are underweight. Anemia is extremely high, affecting over 76% of tribal children. Among women aged 15–49, more than 60% are anemic, and over 30% are undernourished (BMI below 18), which is significantly higher than the state averages of 48% and 23%, respectively. This alarming data highlights the intergenerational cycle of malnutrition.

In 2011, India's ST population as a whole had a sex ratio of 990, much better than the national ratio of 943. The child sex ratio for 0-6 years of age was also significantly better for tribals at 957 than for the country as a whole (919). It was, however, worryingly lower than the overall sex ratio.

TRIBAL SPIRAL					
TOP 5 Literacy rate (%)			TOP 5 Child sex ratio		
Tribe	Zone	Rate	Tribe	Zone	Ratio
Mizo (Lushian) tribes	Mizoram	97.5	Bhottada, Dhotada etc	Orissa	1,007
Kachari, Sonwal	Assam	85.4	Bhuiya, Bhuyan	Orissa	1,002
Dhodia, Dhodi	Maharashtra, Gujarat, Goa	83.7	Gond, Gondo etc	Eastern region	994
Tangkhum	Manipur	82.3	Koya, Doli Koya etc	Andhra Pradesh	994
Tripura, Tripuri etc	Tripura	81.1	Ho	Eastern region	992
BOTTOM 5			BOTTOM 5		
Bakarwal	J&K	31.8	Sugalis	Andhra Pradesh	879
Yenadi, Chella Yenadi etc	Andhra Pradesh	40.8	Mina	Rajasthan	888
Bhil, Bhilala, Barela, Patelia	Madhya Pradesh & Chhattisgarh	42.2	Malayali	Tamil Nadu	888
Kolha	Orissa	42.2	Bakarwal	Jammu & Kashmir	892
Konda Dhoras, Kubi	Andhra Pradesh	45.8	Gujjar	J&K	905

The released data also shows how wide the variation is among tribal communities on a crucial development indicator like literacy. While the overall literacy rate of 59% among STs is much lower than the national average of 73%, individual tribal groups have rates ranging from as high as 97.5% among the Mizo tribes - to as low as 31.8% among the Bakarwals of Jammu & Kashmir. It is also noticeable %is the large gender gap in literacy among STs. India's male literacy rate of 80.9% is about 16 percentage points higher than the female literacy rate of 64.6%.

5. Domestic Violence:

Issues such as violence against women, domestic abuse, and practices like dowry remain serious concerns. Statistics on domestic and tribal violence show high prevalence, with studies indicating that a significant percentage of women experience various forms of violence. For example, a study in India found that 31.2% of women experienced domestic violence between 2019 and 2021, with physical, emotional, and sexual violence reported by 28.5%, 13.1%, and 5.7% of women, respectively. In a tribal community in India, 70.3% of women reported experiencing some form of domestic violence.

Ansari and Rajaram further state that, "The statistics in "Crime in India 2022", the annual report by NCRB, show that a total of 13 States and Union Territories recorded crime rates higher than the national average of 66.4. Delhi topped the list at 144.4, followed by Haryana (118.7), Telangana (117), Rajasthan (115.1), Odisha (103.3), Andhra Pradesh (96.2), Andaman and Nicobar Islands (93.7), Kerala (82), Assam (81.2), Madhya Pradesh (78.8), Uttarakhand (77), Maharashtra (75.1), and West Bengal (71.8). The rate of crime in Uttar Pradesh — which contributed nearly 15 percent of the cases in India — stood at 58.6." On an incidence count-metric, the four worst offending states would be Uttar Pradesh (65743 incidences), Rajasthan (45058), and Maharashtra (45331). Among Union Territories, quite predictably – is Delhi

maintaining its spot as the region with the most number of crimes as it does when it comes to metropolitan cities.

According to *Tristan Gaudiaut*, (Nov 26, 2025), As our infographic also shows, of the more than 365,000 acts of violence against women recorded in 2022 by Indian authorities (National Crime Records Bureau), 38 percent were cruelty by a husband or relatives. In addition, dowry deaths, referring to the deaths of married women resulting from dowry disputes, accounted for 2 percent of reported crimes against women. This brings the proportion of domestic violence in the total number of reported violence against women in India to at least 40 percent, considering underestimation due to unreported cases.

Property and Inheritance Rights

Many women are deprived of their property and inheritance rights because several legal provisions have not yet been adequately reformed.

Economic and Political Issues

- **Economic Exploitation:** The benefits of economic change and development do not reach everyone equally, leading women to become victims of economic exploitation.
- **Workplace Discrimination:** Discrimination at the workplace and the lack of equal pay for equal work remain major problems.
- **Lack of Political Participation:** Many women are excluded from political decision-making processes, causing their issues to be overlooked.

Cultural and Environmental Issues

- **Cultural Practices:** Certain traditional practices, such as genital mutilation, are harmful to women's health.
- **Environmental Changes:** Environmental changes have a significant impact on their lifestyle and livelihood.

Provisions of the Indian constitution inclined towards the tribal population as a whole:

- Part (C) of Article 244(1) says that: The expression 'scheduled tribe' means such areas as the President of India may by order of 1950, 1975 and 1977 declare to be Scheduled Areas[4].
- Article 15(4): Article 15 prohibits any form of discrimination on the grounds of religion, race, sex, caste, birth in any institution maintained by the state. And clause 4 of this article empowers the state to make any special provision Scheduled Classes and Scheduled Tribes.[5]
- Article 16(4): State can make any provision for the reservation of appointments on any posts in favour of any backward class of citizens if not represented adequately.
- Article 19(5): State can impose reasonable restrictions on the exercise of any of the rights either in the interests of the general public or for the protection of the interests of any Scheduled Tribe.
- Prevention of Atrocities Act 1989: This act was enacted to prevent atrocities against the minorities specially scheduled castes & tribes. And this act is known as the Scheduled Tribe and Scheduled Castes (Prevention of Atrocities) Act, 1989.
- Article 23 eliminates the system of bondage, forced labour. Most of the bonded and forced labour belongs to these communities so this article works in favour of these communities.
- Article 29(2): No citizen shall be denied admission to any educational institution maintained by the state fund or receiving aid out of the state funds on the ground of race, religion, caste, language or any of them.[6]
- Article 39: State shall in particular direct its policy towards securing adequate means of livelihood for all and the operation of the economic system does not result in the concentration of wealth and means of production to the common detriment.
- Article 45: State shall endeavour to provide free and compulsory education for all children till the age of 14 years.
- Article 46 talks about the promotion of educational and economic interests of weaker sections of the people and, in particular, of the SCs and STs and especially to protect them from social injustice and exploitation.
- Article 330, 332, 334 and 335 ensure reservation for the SCs and STs in the Lok Sabha and State Legislative Assemblies. Though such reservations were to be ceased on the expiry of a period of 40 years from the commencement of the constitution, i.e. in 1990 (Article 334) but, it has been repeatedly amended and the duration has been extended.

Suggestions

1. Literacy campaign:

A proper awareness campaign should be organized to create awareness about the importance of education. Extensive literacy campaigns in the tribal-dominated districts may be undertaken on a priority basis to literate the tribal.

2. Attitude of the tribal parents:

The attitude of the tribal parents toward education should be improved through proper counselling and guidance. Relevant study materials in local languages - All study materials should be supplied in local languages of tribes.

3. Appointment of Local teachers and female teachers:

It is suggested to appoint more tribal teachers and female teachers in the tribal areas. The ecological, cultural, psychological characteristics of tribal children should be considered carefully by the teachers in tribal areas.

4. Stipends and various scholarships:

Since higher education among the tribes is less, special ST scholarships should be provided to the tribal students pursuing higher education particularly in medical, engineering and other vocational streams; though there are various scholarships and incentives available for the tribal children but either those are not updated properly or there are lacunae in implementation.

5. Residential schools:

More residential schools should be established in each state and districts and extended up to PG level in tribal areas. Social security- Social security of students, especially of adolescent girls is of great concern in residential schools. Proper Monitoring - Higher-level officials should check the functioning of schools frequently relating to the teaching methods, working hours, and attendance registers.

Conclusion

Tribal women in India continue to face multilayered challenges rooted in educational deprivation, language barriers, economic marginalization, poor health infrastructure, and persistent gender-based discrimination. Despite constitutional safeguards, welfare schemes, and legal protections, the benefits have not fully reached remote tribal regions due to systemic gaps in implementation, cultural exclusion, and inadequate political representation. The intergenerational cycle of malnutrition, high maternal and child mortality, domestic violence, and socio-economic vulnerability remains a critical concern. Strengthening mother-tongue education, improving healthcare access, ensuring local teacher recruitment, and expanding residential schooling can significantly uplift tribal communities. Similarly, addressing socio-cultural norms, promoting women's leadership, and guaranteeing property and inheritance rights

are essential for long-term empowerment. Effective monitoring, inclusive governance, and active community participation are necessary to translate constitutional provisions into lived realities. Sustainable progress will be possible only when tribal women gain equal access to education, health, security, and economic opportunities, enabling them to participate fully in nation-building.

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